

Biochar : ameliorant material that environmentally friendly for swampland

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ABSTRACT

Swampland has the potential to be developed as a productive agricultural area. However swampland has several problems, including: low soil fertility caused by acid soil pH, low availability of macro and micro nutrients, poisoning of organic acids on peat soil, iron on submerged acid sulphate soils and Al on oxidized acid sulphate soils. Environmental problems often accompanying swampland use for agriculture are GHG emissions, pesticide residues and reduced soil organism biodiversity. Biochar is a charcoal that contains high carbon, as a result of pyrolysis and is an environmentally friendly ameliorant material. The role of biochar in swampland includes: increasing carbon stocks in the soil and reducing CO₂ release, reducing nutrient leaching through increased buffering capacity, reducing soil acidity, being able to reduce pesticide residues and organic pollutants, reducing the formation of GHG emissions, especially N₂O and methane (CH₄) and improve growth performance and crop yields. This paper reviews the role of biochar in improving the fertility of swamplands and reducing GHG emissions. The ability of biochar to improve soil properties is determined by the type and size of biochar. The finer the size of the biochar, the faster the reaction in the soil, so that it is faster in improving soil properties. The application of biochar in swampland in addition to considering the quality of the material, but also the availability of biochar raw materials. Some types of biochar that can be used include: biochar of rice husk, galam, coconut shell and palm midrib. All types of that biochar are able to reduce GHG emissions, however the effectiveness in improving soil fertility of rice husk biochar is better on acidic sulfate soil and alluvial soil, while for peat soil using coconut shell biochar.

Keywords: *biochar, ameliorant, environmentally friendly, swamplands*

INTRODUCTION

Swamp land has the potential to be developed as a productive agricultural area. However swampland has several problems, among others: low soil fertility caused by acidic soil pH, low availability of macro and micro nutrients, poisoning of organic acids (on peat soil), iron in submerged acid

sulphate soils, and oxidized acid sulphate soils. Environmental problems often accompanying swamp land use for agriculture are GHG emissions, pesticide residues and reduced soil organism biodiversity.

Improving soil fertility in swamp lands is needed to support land productivity. Ameliorant is very important to improve soil fertility in swamp land. However, the development of agriculture in swamp land is often faced with the problem of GHG emissions which are allegedly partly due to amelioration and fertilization (Annisa and Nursyamsi, 2016). The selection of ameliorant materials that can improve soil fertility and at the same time reduce GHG emissions is important in the effort to use swamp land.

Biochar was alleged to be able to reduce GHG emissions (Mukherjee and Lal, 2013). Biochar was able to improve the soil through its ability to increase pH, increase water holding capacity, nutrients, and increase the activity of biota in the soil and reduce pollution (Laird et al., 2010). However, biochar was unable to provide nutrients directly, but indirectly could reduce nutrient losses through leaching, so that fertilization efficiency could be increased.

Biochar is an alternative material for improving soil fertility, as well as improving the environment that is cheap, sustainable and environmentally friendly. Biochar can improve soil chemical, physical and biological properties. N fertilizer loss through fertilization could be reduced by the addition of biochar (Steiner et al., 2007). The nutritional content of biochar was influenced by the basic ingredients used in the manufacturing process, especially the temperature and time of manufacture (Lehmann and Joseph, 2009).

The role of biochar is not only as a nutrient contributor, but also its main role as a soil enhancer. Biochar is able to provide a combination of air and water which is good for the growth of microbes that play a role in the soil. Biochar could also be used as an effective carrier for microbes that play an important role in the soil, so that they can play a role in making biological fertilizers (Santi and Goenadi, 2010). Fungi could sporulate in biochar micro pores because in the pore the competition that occurs with other saprophytes is quite low (Saito and Marumoto, 2002).

This paper reviews the role of biochar in improving the productivity of swamps, as well as its ability to reduce GHG emissions in swampland.

Biochar from Organic Materials in Swampland

Swamplands in Indonesia are generally typical, located between terrestrial areas and deep aquatic systems. Swampland was land that is throughout the year or for a long time in a year, always saturated with water or stagnant (Subagyo, 2006). Ecologically of swampland was a habitat where

various flora and fauna living creatures develop. As stated by Mukhlis et al (2014), the typical swamp conditions affected the development of flora specifically.

Swamp land wasn't only overgrown by typical plants of swamps, among others. kalakai (*Stenochlaena palustris*), karamunting (*Melastomataceae*), galam (*Melaleuca leucandra*), purun tikus (*Eleocharis dulcis*), but also plants that have been cultivated in swamps, among others; rice (*oryza sativa*), oil palm (*Elaeis guineensis*), coconut (*Cocos nucifera*), various types of palawija and horticulture. Various types of plants can be used as organic material for biochar raw materials. Agricultural waste or crop residue in the form of rice husk, palm oil shells, coconut shells, palm fronds can also be used as biochar raw materials.

Biochar is a product of thermal decomposition of organic material under oxygen-limited condition and at relatively low temperature (<700°C), and used as soil amendment (Sohi et al., 2009; Lehmann and Joseph, 2009). The chemical and physical properties of biochar depend on its feedstock type and pyrolysis condition such as temperature, time duration, and air supply (Sohi et al., 2009).

The ash content of biochar also varied depend on the type of biochar. According to Maftuah and Nursyamsi (2015), ash content was positively related to the lignin content of the material (Figure 1). SiO₂ content was positively related to lignin content and forms a quadratic relationship according to the equation $Y = 0.030x^2 - 1355x + 54.76$ ($R^2 = 0.763$). The composition of the biochar ash fraction was largely dependent on minerals in the raw material, because most of the inorganic elements didn't evaporate at the pyrolysis temperature (Brewer, 2012). Raw materials and pyrolysis processes determined the amount and distribution of mineral materials in biochar (Amonette and Joseph, 2009).

Materials derived from wood generally had low ash content (<1 percent by weight), while grass, straw and seeds (husks) had a high silica content of up to 24% (Raveendran et al., 1995). Most of the mineral content in the raw material was still present in biochar and partially lost (i.e. C, H and O) during pyrolysis. Biochar from organic fertilizer and waste usually had a very high ash content. Biochar of chicken manure had 45% ash from raw materials (Koutcheiko et al., 2007), and bone biochar contained minerals reaching 84% of minerals from raw materials (Purevsuren et al., 2004).

Figure 1. Relation of biochar ash content and SiO₂ with lignin and cellulose content of biochar materials (Maftuah and Nursyamsi, 2015)

Based on the results of Balittra's research (2014), biochar raw materials affected the characteristics of biochar produced (Table 1). Rice husk biochar had a higher CEC compared to biochar from coconut shells, galam, palm fronds and oil palm bunches. Different raw materials had different qualities, especially the content of lignin, cellulose, hemicellulos and C/N ratio (Maftuah and Nursyamsi, 2015).

Biochar characteristics were not only determined by the raw material, but also the pyrolysis process. Temperature, partial pressure O₂, and carbon dioxide (CO₂) controled the amount of mineral ash in biochar (Bridgwater and Boocock, 2006). During thermal degradation, very mobile ions (example K and Cl) would begin to evaporate at relatively low temperatures (Yu et al., 2005). Calcium (Ca) was mainly located on the cell wall and was bound to organic acids (Marschner, 1995). Ca and Si were released during degradation at temperatures higher than K and Cl (Bourke, 2006). Magnesium (Mg) was both ionic and covalent bound to organic molecules and only evaporates at high temperatures. Phosphorus (P) and sulfur (S) were associating with complex organic compounds in cells and were relatively stable at low temperatures. Nitrogen was associating with a number of different organic molecules and could be released at relatively low temperatures (Schnitzer et al., 2007). Other elements such as Fe and Mn were largely retained during biochar formation (Amonette and Joseph, 2009).

Table 1. Characteristics of biochar from various sources of raw materials

Type of biochar	C/N	pH	CEC	SiO ₂	Ash content	N	P	K	Ca	Mg	Fe	Water content
			Cmol/kg							%		
Rice husk	43,92	8,99	37,38	34,83	44,35	0,73	0,48	0,54	0,21	0,18	0,26	5,10
Palm bunches	42,76	9,39	9,93	4,90	27,09	0,99	0,49	8,65	0,43	0,67	0,53	7,19
Bamboo	49,54	9,30	9,30	3,21	11,26	1,04	0,45	3,18	0,16	0,13	0,16	5,81
Palm midrib	39,64	9,74	9,74	6,30	31,17	1,01	0,39	1,53	0,53	0,96	0,15	9,19
Coconut shell	23,20	9,61	9,61	4,04	48,96	1,28	0,52	2,96	0,29	4,43	0,29	5,87
Palm oil	27,28	8,30	8,30	3,90	59,32	0,87	0,44	0,72	0,09	0,30	0,04	3,49
Galam stem	83,46	9,04	9,04	2,13	23,15	0,54	0,42	1,14	0,43	0,05	0,14	5,56

Source: Balittra, 2014

One of the physical properties of biochar can be known from the particle size and biochar pore. Biochar pore size can be measured using Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM). SEM analysis results of several biochar as presented in Figure 2. The particle size produced at the heating rate (temperature 400 °C) was not much different from the particle size of the raw material before pyrolysis. However, some volatile substances were lost during pyrolysis, so biochar becomes more porous (Brewer, 2012).

Brown, et al. (2006) showed that biochar density was independent of heating rate, and found a simple and direct dependency of density upon final pyrolysis temperature. The biochar particle size produced from pyrolysis of organic matter is very dependent on the nature of the raw material. Because of both shrinkage and friction during pyrolysis, the particle size of the raw material for organic materials tends to be greater than the biochar produced. In some cases, particles could clot; therefore, an increase in particle size was also found (Cetin et al., 2004).

Figure 2. Pore size and SEM photo particle size of several types of biochar

Based on the results of SEM analysis, coconut shell biochar had a composition of micro, meso and macro pore spaces that is more than bamboo

biochar, purun tikus and palm midrib biochar. Rice husk biochar shown more particles than pores. Biochar galam shown more macro pores than micro or particle pores.

There are differences in particle size in each biochar. The biochar particle size produced from pyrolysis of organic matter is very dependent on the nature of the original material. This is due to shrinkage and friction during pyrolysis, so that the biochar particle size tends to be greater than the original material and in some cases, particles can clot which causes the particle size to increase (Cetin et al., 2004).

The Role of Biochar in Improving Characteristic and Productivity of Swamplands

Biochar could improve soil fertility and sequester C (Sohi et al., 2010), increasing pH (Topoliantz et al., 2007; Yuan et al., 2011), improved nutrient availability (Chan et al., 2008;), nutrient retention (Lehmann et al., 2003), and cation-exchange capacity (Masulili et al., 2010; Yuan et al., 2011) of soil. Lehmann et al. (2003) explained that biochar was able to improve fertilizer efficiency. Giving biochar would add negative and positive charges that could absorb several ions in the soil solution. As reported by Proctor (2003) that changes in the concentration of cations in soil solutions were influenced by the interaction of these ions with the active functional group of peat.

Biochar could improve soil chemical, physical and biological properties. N loss through fertilization could be reduced by the addition of biochar (Steiner, 2007). Biochar was able to increase the availability of nutrients for plants and crop productivity (Glaser et al., 2002). However, the specific mechanism of biochar's contribution to P availability and emissions on peat soil had not been widely disclosed. The effect of adding biochar to soil respiration and CO₂ emissions varied (Zimmerman, 2010), depend on the type of biochar, soil type and soil organic C content (Steiner et al., 2008).

Table. 2. Effect of biochar types on the nature of peat soil

	Galam stem	Palm midrib	Rice husk	Coconut Shell
pH	4.18	4.13	4.16	4.14
Organic C (%)	49.07	48.14	51.91	51.01
P available (mg/kg)	268.79	243.67	86.47	150.88
K-exe (cmol/kg)	0.518	0.798	0.088	1.178

Source : Balittra (2014)

Biochar could improve the storage of P nutrient in peat soils whose effectiveness depended on the type of biochar. Coconut shell biochar and karamunting biochar was able to increase the storage capacity of P in peat soil. Biochar which could reduce emissions was coconut shell biochar, galam biochar and bamboo. Biochar coconut shells could increase the storage of P and simultaneously reduce emissions on peat soil (Maftuah and Nurita, 2016). Biochar had been proven to function to absorb carbon to mitigate global climate change effects (Zheng et al., 2012), maintaining soil nitrogen to reduce eutrophic nutrient loading in aquatic ecosystems (Zheng et al., 2013) and reducing contaminants to protect biotic environments land (Wang et al., 2012).

Coconut shell biochar gave the same effect as ameliorant in the form of 80% dolomite + 20% chicken manure on maize production on peatlands (Table 3). Rice husk biochar could improve yields compared to farmers and control methods. Ameliorant in the form 50% rice husk biochar + 50% chicken manure, with a dose of 5 t/ha was able to increase P and K uptake and reduce CO₂ emissions by 22% and N₂O by 30% in maize plantations on peatlands. The yield of maize on peat land used biochar reached 5.8 dry weight grain t/ha, the way of the farmer (3.6 t / ha), while the control or without ameliorant was 0.05 t /ha) (Balittra, 2013).

Table 3. Effect of biochar on maize yield on peatlands

Amelioran type	Number of lines/cob	Number of seeds/rows	Weight of 100 seeds (g)	Dry shell yield (t/ha)
80% chicken manure+20% dolomite	11,93 ab	38,5 a	26,3 a	5,82 a
100% rice husk biochar	10,87 b	32,6 bc	25,3 b	4,29 bc
100% coconut shell biochar	11,80 ab	36,8 bc	26,3 ab	5,71 a
Farmer's way	11,20 ab	32,7 c	23,7 b	3,59 c
Control	9,16 c	20,9 d	19,8 c	1,39 d

Source : Simatupang et al., 2016

The application of biochar on peatland shown that rice husk biochar+chicken manure each dose of 7.5 t/ha could increase the production of shallots by 2.5 x greater than the control (cow manure), and reduce CO₂ emissions by 30%. The results of onion Bauji variety that used rice husk biochar on peat land reaches 9 t/ha (Balittra, 2017). Providing biochar could replace phosphate rock in peatland restoration, adding biochar from pig manure as much as 3-9 g/m³ could reduce natural phosphate by 15 g/m³ (Pouliot et al., 2015). Improvement of the chemical and hydrophysical properties of peat could

be done by adding biochar. Biochar increased air space, holds water capacity and increased lettuce yields by more than 100% (Mendez et al., 2015).

The application of rice husk biochar combined with multiorganic compost in acid sulphate land could increase efficiency of the use of NPK fertilizer up to 50% and increase rice yield by 36.8% with using varieties Inpara 3, 38.6% using inpari 30 varieties and 2.17% using Siam Mutiara varieties (Annisa, 2016). Rice husk biochar had a significant effect on acid sulphate soil fertility, ie pH with a dose of biochar 15 g/5 kg of soil, exch-Fe at a dose of 30 g/5 kg of soil and exch-Al with a dose of 37.5 g/5 kg of soil and didn't significant effect on the CEC, exch-Fe . Biochar of oil palm bunches had a significant effect on pH at a dose of 15 g/5 kg of soil, exch-Fe at a dose of 15 g/5 kg of soil and exch-Al at a dose of 15 g/5 kg of soil and didn't give significant effect on CEC, exch-Fe and exch-Al (Agustina, 2017).

Biochar also had a positive effect on the productivity of the swampy land. Based on research by Saputra et al. (2016), giving rice husk biochar obtained the highest N-total soil uptake of 0.33% with rice plant Nitrogen uptake of 3.34 grams per plot and having optimal rice plant growth compared to coconut shell biochar treatment or without biochar.

The Role of Biochar in Agricultural Environmentally Friendly in Swamplands

Biochar is an increasingly popular topic in environmental management due to its potential effects on several ecosystem functions. Specifically, biochar has been linked to significant reductions in greenhouse gas emissions, including nitrous oxide, carbon dioxide and methane when used as a soil amendment. It has also been suggested as a long term mechanism to sequester carbon in soil. The magnitude of such an effect is highly dependent on a variety of environmental factors, as well as the feedstock and temperature at which the char was produced, so it is essential to put biochar studies in specific land use contexts to fully understand its potential impacts (Keenan, 2016).

CH_4 emissions from rice cultivation in acid sulphate land could be reduced by using rice husk biochar combined with multiorganic compost by 38.8% (Annisa, 2016). According to Yu et al., 2012 the effect of biochar on CH_4 emissions was related to the soil moisture caused by the addition of biochar. Besides soil moisture, methane production and consumption is affected by soil microbial activity.

Figure 3. Effect of biochar on CO₂ and CH₄ emissions in swampland (Balittra, 2014; Annisa, 2016).

Addition of biochar in the soil could reduce Cd accumulated in plant tissues (Zang et al. 2012). It was further explained that biochars immobilize Cd in the soil, however didn't increase the growth of wetland plant species that appear at the initial growth stage. Biochar was effective in metal immobilization, thereby reducing the bioavailability and phytotoxicity of heavy metals (Park et al., 2011). Biochar had a large surface area, and high capacity to absorb heavy metals and organic pollutants (Zhang et al., 2013). Biochar was usually an alkaline material that could increase soil pH and contribute to the stabilization of heavy metals. The application of biochar to remediate contaminated soil could provide new solutions to the problem of soil pollution in swamp land. The effectiveness of biochar in remediating heavy metals was also closely related to soil redox conditions and oxygen-containing biochar functional groups (Rinklebe et al., 2015).

CONCLUSIONS

Biochar is a material that can improve soil fertility, soil productivity and reduce GHG emissions and remediate heavy metals in swamps. Biochar can be used as an alternative material to create an environmentally friendly farming system in swamplands. The effectiveness of biochar in improving soil fertility, crop production and improving the environment of swamps depends on the type of biochar, biochar size, the process of making biochar (pyrolysis

temperature), and soil conditions, especially soil types and redox potential. One type of biochar may be suitable for application to certain types of soil, but not suitable for other types of soil. Some types of biochar that can be used include: biochar of rice husk, galam, coconut shell and palm midrib. All types of that biochar are able to reduce GHG emissions, however the effectiveness in improving soil fertility of rice husk biochar is better on acidic sulfate soil and alluvial soil, while for peat soil using coconut shell biochar is better. Biochar is also capable of remediating swamp land contaminated with heavy metals, and its effectiveness depends on the type of biochar (functional group) and soil redox potential.

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